

Downey and Tucker "Breed differences in oral behaviors in feed-restricted dairy heifers"

Supplemental Table S1. Raw means, SE, and 95% CI for all oral behaviors scored, along with model outputs.

Raw behavior means (proportions), CI, and betaregression model results:

Behavior	Breed				DF	Betareg model results	
	Holstein		Jersey			chisq	P-value
	Mean (SE)	95% CI	Mean (SE)	95% CI			
NNOM: Other	0.042 (0.004)	[0.034,0.050]	0.075 (0.013)	[0.044,0.105]	1,39	8.911	0.003
NNOM: Bedding	0.054 (0.006)	[0.042,0.066]	0.077 (0.008)	[0.059,0.096]	1,39	6.164	0.013
NNOM: Feed bin	0.024 (0.002)	[0.019,0.028]	0.038 (0.004)	[0.029,0.047]	1,39	12.740	<0.001
NNOM: Total	0.120 (0.006)	[0.108,0.133]	0.190 (0.019)	[0.147,0.233]	1,39	23.476	<0.001
Tongue flicks	0.011 (0.001)	[0.009,0.013]	0.014 (0.002)	[0.009,0.019]	1,39	3.261	0.071
Groom: Allo	0.034 (0.003)	[0.028,0.039]	0.013 (0.005)	[0.0004,0.025]	1,39	18.957	<0.001
Groom: Self	0.021 (0.001)	[0.019,0.023]	0.019 (0.004)	[0.011,0.027]	1,39	1.247	0.264
Drinking water	0.015 (0.001)	[0.012,0.017]	0.014 (0.002)	[0.010,0.018]	1,39	0.014	0.905
Eating	0.160 (0.004)	[0.153,0.168]	0.158 (0.007)	[0.143,0.173]	1,39	0.059	0.808

Behavior	Breed						unpaired Wilcoxon test results	
	Holstein		# doing behavior	Jersey		# doing behavior	P-value	W value
	Means (SE)	95% CI		Means (SE)	95% CI			
Intersucking	0.00062 (0.0002)	[0.0003,0.0009]	23 (70%)	0.00066 (0.0004)	[0,0.002]	7 (78%)	0.879	143
Tongue rolling	0.002 (0.002)	[0.0008,0.003]	33 (100%)	0.033 (0.064)	[0,0.082]	9 (100%)	0.018	225

Additional behaviors not modeled:

	Breed			
	Holstein		Jersey	
	Means (SE)	# doing behavior	Means (SE)	# doing behavior
Urine drinking	0.00003 (0.00001)	6 (18%)	0.00003 (0.00002)	3 (33%)